

EFFECTIVE USE AND ENJOYMENT OF EDUCATION

Nurmatov Islombek Qizilbek o'g'li

Jizzax viloyati yuridik texnikumi o'qituvchisi

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Abstract. This article will talk about the effective use of the educational system, pleasure and the importance of education in the updated Uzbekistan, as well as about reforms in the educational system.

Key words: educational system, enjoyment, reforms, lesson processes, interests.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАСЛАЖДЕНИЕ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается об эффективном использовании системы образования, получении удовольствия и важности образования в обновляющемся Узбекистане, а также о реформах в системе образования.

Ключевые слова: система образования, получение удовольствия, реформы, процессы урока, интересы.

From the first years of independence in our country, the development of the educational system has risen to the level of state policy, and great works are being carried out in order to ensure that our children acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions corresponding to World templates, grow up to be physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities and talents, intellectual potential.

As you know, in order to further improve the educational system of our country, accelerate the development of the field of Science, a draft presidential decree was developed. This document regulation.gov.uz it was put on the portal and widely discussed in all regions, local councils and school communities with the participation of parents. The draft decree covers goals that will solve current problems in education, show the result in the next five years and determine the level of further progress.

In particular, solutions to such issues as raising the reputation and status of a teacher in society, a complete revision of curricula and methodology, inextricably linking the school with the later stages of education, creating conditions for teachers to work more on themselves, ridding them of excess paperwork and encouraging this, improving the school infrastructure and spiritual atmosphere in it are clearly defined. The main thing is to radically change the approach and focus of leaders on the site, as well as local councils on this important issue, introducing mechanisms of their responsibility, responsibility and accountability.

To enjoy education, make the following important recommendations:
Explore interesting topics: in the educational process, choose topics that are close to your own topic. It will be more interesting and amazing than the science you want. To do this, interest yourself in interests and lifestyle interests in what areas.

Refrain from practice: practice means that it is very important to realize your knowledge. Trust the information you have learned, current in practice on elected topics. It is not enough to know most of the time, make it a habit for yourself to use it to strengthen the data in practice.

Discussion: join different conversations in classes or books on the topics you are studying. Ask questions about your time in class or ask questions to the author at the end of the lesson. Share your thoughts, thoughts, advice and advice in a group, with loved ones, or on the internet.

Organize life on an educational basis: organize your life and organize your time on the basis of Education. You will think or record the necessary information and skills by creating the right plan and following it. This will put order in your learning process and you will feel that this content is easy to learn.

Create and develop: try to become a creator in the educational process and develop the information you have learned. Try to create your own thoughts on the topic, business ideas. This Will Make Your Education easy and fun.

Applying your disclosure in education: it is very important to help other students to participate in learning. Teaching your learning skills to other people, sharing thoughts with them, and connecting your own thoughts will expand your knowledge and enlightenment. Stick to it by learning how to help other people.

Be careful with knowledge: careful education is a must. There is no way to overtake learning too quickly. You will need time to achieve the highest results. Try to know more differently, in practice record the entries and bring notes, create for yourself the list of recorded and learned.

Setting: always set goals in the learning process. Light goals for yourself, tasks broken into your habits and work over past programs. Set a goal for each week, month or year and follow the result.

To enjoy education, take unborn courses, improve support skills and get interested in areas that are consumed in Uzbek and foreign formats, in which you can work in the future. Remember, enjoying education expands the tone and possibilities of life.

Find a love for the topic: to get a breakthrough in any topic of your own, find topics that will come to you well. This will make education more fun and motivating for you.

You mark your reading on the first part of a topic or two in your study, and then create an internal motivation to achieve the goals set for yourself in the learning process.

It is recommended that you put the information under study into practice: in order for theoretical education to have a better understanding, you put the information under study into practice. This will help you understand what you have learned through many activities and examples.

You can put your interests into practice: you can learn by including yourself in activities that are linked to your interests, motivate yourself and increase your enjoyment.

Group collaboration: group teacher or student interaction has a specific place of interaction in the learning process. Allows topics to be communicated, spoken, and explored with a group.

You can enter the data in different ways: you can use different activities and tools to help you give the data in the way you can start. This is one of the many ways that books, magazines, internet data, podcasts, videos, etc. can be used to store, understand, and share learned information with the public.

Set yourself goals that make you enjoy education: setting your own goals and paths in the educational process is the main condition for enjoying education in its legal physical aspect. With our goals, it should be parallel to local, national and international reforms.

Discussion and disciplined listening: think with the information you are learning, it would be necessary for some readers to respond or organize. This increases the inherent pleasure of education in the face of the attentive and deservedly worked appearance of the educational material.

Being a manifestation of life: in order to increase pleasure in education, it is necessary to provide a connection with learning within the framework of life. This strengthens the adequacy, wonders and interests of the age you like about learning.

Try to be the same in educational work if you have a special significance of words older than yourself. This will help, firstly, discover your reading and achievement characteristics, and, secondly, define your learning criteria for yourself.

It was noted that it is important to introduce modern curricula, teaching methodologies in the world and introduce them in secondary schools of our country. To the Ministry of public education on the basis of this experience

In conclusion, all the conditions for reading, learning, learning are being created-now it is more than ever necessary for us to grow up as a child, a frame, an expert person, who will be confident in the next day, and determine the future of our people, our motherland, and work more on ourselves in response to these initiatives put forward by our president.

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